

**ROLE OF AYURVEDA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF DRUG-INDUCED DERMATITIS: A
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ABSTRACT

Drug-induced dermatitis is a common adverse cutaneous reaction caused by systemic or topical drug administration, ranging from mild erythema to severe inflammatory lesions.^[1] It is considered as an immune-mediated hypersensitivity reaction involving inflammatory mediators and altered immune responses.^[2] *Ayurveda* explains such conditions under *Twak Vikara*, or *Visha-janya Kustha*, where *Garavisha*, *Pitta*, and *Rakta* play a key role in pathogenesis.^[3] Improper digestion and metabolism of drugs lead to accumulation of toxic substances, resulting in cutaneous manifestations.^[4] This case report highlights the successful management of drug-induced dermatitis through *Ayurvedic* principles including *Shodhana* and *Shamana* therapies, along with appropriate dietary and lifestyle modifications. The treatment aimed at *Vishahara*, *Raktashodhana*, and *Pittashamana* resulted in marked clinical improvement without adverse effects, suggesting *Ayurveda* as a safe and holistic therapeutic approach.^[5]

KEYWORDS: Garavisha, Drug-induced toxicity, Dermatitis, Drug-induced dermatitis.**INTRODUCTION**

Drug-induced dermatitis is a frequent dermatological adverse reaction associated with medications such as antibiotics, NSAIDs, and anticonvulsants.^[1] It is mediated by immunological mechanisms leading to inflammation of the skin, presenting with erythema, pruritus, and rashes.^[2] In *Ayurveda*, such manifestations are described under *Twak Vikara* and *Visha-janya Vyadhi*, particularly involving *Garavisha*, where toxins vitiate *Rakta* and *Pitta*, producing inflammatory skin changes.^[3] *Ayurvedic* management focuses on eliminating toxins, pacifying aggravated *Doshas*, and restoring tissue homeostasis through *Shodhana* and *Shamana* therapies, offering a comprehensive and integrative approach to disease management.^[5]

CASE REPORT

A 36-year-old female reported to the *Vishachikitsa* OPD at Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara College of Ayurveda & Hospital, Hassan, presenting with multiple

maculo-papular lesions in the sun-exposed areas of bilateral forearms and nape of the neck, along with severe redness, burning sensation and itching since 3 weeks. The patient had a history of fever before 3 weeks and took paracetamol for the same, after which, the symptoms occurred. Despite prior allopathic consultation, the patient reported no clinically significant improvement in symptoms.

General Examination

- Temperature: 97 F
- Pulse rate: 90 bpm
- Blood pressure: 130/90 mmHg
- Respiratory System: Chest clear
- Circulatory System: S1, S2 heard, no murmurs
- Central Nervous System: Conscious and oriented
- P/A: soft and non tender

Local Examination

- Site: B/L forearms and nape of the neck

- Shape: Circular
- Colour: Reddish
- Number: multiple
- Associated symptoms: Redness, severe burning sensation and moderate itching
- Type of lesion: maculo-papule

Ashta sthana pareeksha

- **Nadi:** Pitta kapha
- **Mala:** Regular bowel
- **Mutra:** occasionally associated with burning sensation
- **Jihva:** Alipta
- **Shabda:** Spashta
- **Sparsha:** Ushna in the affected areas

- **Drik:** Prakruta
- **Akruti:** Madhyama

Dashavidha pareeksha

- **Prakruti:** Vata pitta
- **Vikruti:** Pitta kapha
- **Sara:** Madhyama
- **Samhanana:** Madhyama
- **Satva:** Madhyama
- **Satmya:** Madhyama
- **Ahara shakti:** Madhyama
- **Vyayama shakti:** Madhyama
- **Vaya:** Madhyama
- **Bala:** Madhyama

Figure 1: Showing clinical presentation on day 1 of admission.

Management

Table 1: Showing Shamana Oushadhi (for 7 days)

SL.NO	SHAMANA OUSHADHI	DOSE	TIME
1.	Chitrakadi vati	1-0-1	Before food
2.	Bilwadi gulika	1-1-1	Before food

Table 2: Showing treatment procedures.

SL.NO	PROCEDURES	DAYS
1.	Sneha basti with Panchatikta guggulu ghrita (80ml, 100ml, 120ml)	3 days
2.	Sarvanga Abhyanga with Nalpamaradi taila	6 days
3.	Sarvanga Bhashpa sweda	6 days
4.	Virechana with Avipattikara choorna 30g on 17/09/2025 (11 vegas)	1 day

Table 3: Discharge medications.

SL.NO	SHAMANA OUSHADHI	DOSE	TIME
1.	Patolakaturohinyadi kashaya	15ml-0-15ml	Before food
2.	Gandhaka rasayana	1-0-1	After food
3.	Nalpamaradi taila	once	Before food
4.	D sora lotion	once	for external application at morning

Figure 2: Showing clinical presentation at the time of discharge.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

Table 4: Observation and symptoms.

DAY	KANDU	RAGA	DAHA
1st	+++	+++++	++++
7th	+	-	-

DISCUSSION

Drug-induced dermatitis is an inflammatory condition resulting from adverse reactions to synthetic or chemical substances.^[1] In the present case, the symptoms initiated post intake of Paracetamol. This clinical condition can be conceptualised with *Garavisha* in Ayurveda. *Garavisha* refers to artificially prepared or incompatible toxic substances that produce harmful effects in the body.^[7] Hence, the treatment protocol was planned based on the principles of *Garavisha Chikitsa*, focusing on *Vishahara*, *Agni Deepana*, *Raktashodhana*, and *Pittashamana*.^[8]

Initial *Shamana Oushadhi* such as *Chitrakadi Vati* and *Bilwadi Gulika* were administered to improve *Agni*, *digest Ama*, and neutralize toxic metabolites formed due to drug intake.^[9] *Bilwadi gulika* is also specific to *Garavisha*.^[10] Both of these formulations possess *Deepana*, *Pachana*, and *Vishaghna* properties, facilitating detoxification and preventing further tissue damage.

Sneha Basti was adopted as the patient was hesitant to take *Sneha pana*. As *Panchatikta Guggulu Ghrita* pacifies *Pitta* and *Vata*, and purify *Rakta* and *Twak*,^[11] it was opted for *sneha basti*, in *Aarohana matra* of 80ml, 100ml and 120ml respectively. *Sarvanga Abhyanga* with *Nalpamaradi Taila* followed by *Bhashpa Sweda* helped in reducing inflammation, burning sensation, and pruritus by improving peripheral circulation.

Virechana with *Avipattikara Choorna* acted as the principal *Shodhana* therapy for expelling aggravated *Pitta* and accumulated toxins.^[12] Eventhough *Vamana* is the *chikitsa* mentioned for *Garavisha* in classics^[13], *Virechana* is opted considering *satva* and *bala* of the

patient. As the symptoms were *Pitta* predominant, *Avipattikara choorna* was the ideal *virechana oushadhi* for this condition. Post-discharge medications such as *Patolakaturohinyadi Kashaya* which is *Kaphapittahara*^[14] and *Gandhaka Rasayana* which acts as *rasayana* and also *twachya* to enhance skin regeneration, and prevented recurrence.^[15] Overall, the integrative application of *Shodhana* and *Shamana* therapies proved effective in managing drug-induced dermatitis with sustained clinical improvement.

CONCLUSION

The present case study demonstrates that drug-induced dermatitis can be effectively correlated with *Garavisha* in *Ayurveda* and successfully managed through appropriate Ayurvedic interventions. The combined application of *Shodhana* therapy, particularly *Virechana*, along with *Shamana Oushadhi* and external therapies resulted in significant clinical improvement without adverse effects. The treatment addressed the underlying pathogenesis by eliminating accumulated toxins, pacifying aggravated *Pitta* and *Rakta*, and restoring tissue homeostasis. This case highlights the potential role of *Ayurveda* as a safe and effective approach in the management of drug-induced dermatological conditions and encourages further clinical studies for evidence-based validation.

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